

Some Newer Cyanoethylated Alkyl Substituted Malonanilides, Ethylmalonanilates and Toluene Sulphonamides as Insecticides: Part II

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Several α -alkyl- α -(β -cyanoethyl) malonanilides and ethyl malonanilates have been synthesized. The evaluation of insecticidal activity of these compounds showed that some of them possess a potential insecticidal property.

CYANOETHYLATION studies of ethylacetate and substituted ethylmalonates have been reported by Misra and Shukla¹, Cooker *et al.*² respectively. The biological activity of these compounds showed that all of them possess more or less insecticidal property. The earlier work of Misra and Asthana³ and Shukla and Srivastava⁴ described cyanoethylated sulphones and sulphonamides as insecticides.

Our continuing interest in incorporating a cyanoethyl group, capable of exhibiting biological activity, has prompted us to extend this study to mono-alkylmalonanilides, ethyl malonanilate, malontoluidide, ethyl malontoluidate and other compounds. They were cyanoethylated in the usual manner with a view to find out some more potential insecticides. Some of these compounds were screened for their insecticidal activity against adult house flies. They were found to possess sufficient insecticidal activity. The results are summarized below.

Experimental

Cyanoethylation of methyl malonanilide to α -methyl- α -(β -cyanoethyl) malondianilide

To a stirred solution containing methyl malondianilide (2.5 g), dioxane (10 ml) and 40% trimethylbenzylammonium hydroxide (0.3 g) was added dropwise acrylonitrile (0.3 g). The mixture was stirred for 15 hr and the product was neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid and poured on 1 : 1 ice water. The solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol in colourless crystals : yield 2.2 g (88%), m.p. 180°-181°.

Analysis

Found : Nitrogen 12.94%. $C_{10}H_{13}N_2O_2$ requires, Nitrogen, 13.08%.

Similarly the compounds mentioned in Table 1 were cyanoethylated.

All the data about the reported compounds are given in Table 1.

Method of testing insecticidal activity

5% solution of the compound in mineral turpentine was used for examining the insecticidal activity. This solution (1 ml) was sprayed by means of aerospray gun at a predetermined pressure into a glass jar containing ten house flies which were kept on a revolving table and covered with mosquito netting.

In control 1 ml of pure mineral turpentine was sprayed. The maximum 50% knock down time was recorded.

The results of screening of insecticidal activity against house flies are summarised in Tables 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6.

Results and Discussion

The ability of various cyanoethylated sulphonamides to exhibit insecticidal activity is shown in Table 3. The activity of these compounds has been compared with well known insecticides DDT, BHC, and pyrethrum (Table 2).

As is evident from Table 4 all ethyl- α -ethyl- α -(2-cyanoethyl) malonanilate derivative were all found to possess significant insecticidal activity. It appears from these results that substituents at different positions of the aromatic ring have a pronounced effect on the insecticidal property.

The maximum insecticidal activity in Table 5 was observed with α -methyl- α -(2-cyanoethyl) malondianilide. Introduction of any other substituent in the aromatic nucleus resulted in lowering of the insecticidal activity.

The most active compound of this series (Table 6) was found to be α -ethyl- α -(2 cyanoethyl)-malon-4,4'-

TABLE 1. PRODUCTS OBTAINED ON CYANOETHYLATION OF ALKYL SUBSTITUTED MALONDIANILIDES AND ETHYL MALONANILIDES

Starting Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula of product	Nitrogen %	
				Found	Required
<i>α-Methyl-α-(β-cyanoethyl-malondianilides, ditoluidides and di-o-anisidide</i>					
Methylmalon-di-(<i>p,p'</i> -dichloro)-anilide	251	75	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	10.78	10.76
Methylmalon-di-(<i>o,o'</i> -dichloro)-anilide	66—68	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	10.80	10.76
Methylmalon-di- <i>p</i> -toluidide	215	80	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	12.05	12.03
Methylmalon-di- <i>o</i> -toluidide	225—227	77	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	12.04	12.03
Methylmalon-di- <i>m</i> -toluidide	195	70	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	12.10	12.03
Methylmalon-di- <i>p</i> -anisidide	214	72	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄	10.95	11.02
<i>Ethyl-α-methyl-α-(β-cyanoethyl)malonoanilate and toluidates</i>					
Ethyl-α-methylmalon- <i>p</i> -chloroanilate	144—45	76	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₃	9.12	9.07
Ethyl-α-methylmalon- <i>o</i> -chloroanilate	130—32	71	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₃	9.12	9.07
Ethyl-α-methylmalon- <i>o</i> -toluidate	146	80	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	9.83	9.72
Ethyl-α-methylmalon- <i>m</i> -toluidate	153—54	72	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	9.82	9.72
Ethyl-α-methylmalon- <i>p</i> -anisidate	163—64	78	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	9.14	9.21
<i>α-Ethyl-α-(β-cyanoethyl)malondianilides and di-toluidides</i>					
Ethylmalon-di-(<i>p,p'</i> -dichloro)anilide	247	82	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	10.41	10.39
Ethylmalon-di-(<i>o,o'</i> -dichloro)anilide	210	74	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	10.42	10.39
Ethylmalon-di-(<i>m,m'</i> -dichloro)anilide	191—92	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	10.45	10.39
Ethylmalon- <i>p</i> -toluidide	232—33	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	11.48	11.57
Ethylmalon- <i>o</i> -toluidide	145—57	72	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	11.60	11.57
Ethylmalon- <i>m</i> -toluidide	174—75	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	11.60	11.57
<i>Ethyl-α-ethyl-α-(β-cyanoethyl)malonnanilates and toluidates</i>					
Ethyl-α-ethylmalon- <i>p</i> -chloroanilate	96	90	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₃	8.72	8.68
Ethyl-α-ethylmalon- <i>o</i> -chloroanilate	290	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₃	8.71	8.68
Ethyl-α-ethylmalon- <i>m</i> -chloroanilate	200	73	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₃	8.72	8.68
Ethyl-α-ethylmalon- <i>p</i> -toluidate	78—79	90	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	9.61	9.58
Ethyl-α-ethylmalon- <i>m</i> -toluidate	205—06	85	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	9.57	9.58
Ethyl-α-ethylmalon- <i>o</i> -toluidate	118—20	70	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	9.61	9.58

TABLE 2. INSECTICIDAL ACTIVITY OF REFERENCE COMPOUNDS

Sl. No.	Name of compound	Concentration %	Mean 50% knockdown time in seconds
1.	D.D.T. in mineral turpentine	0.5	305
2.	B.H.C. in mineral turpentine	0.5	300
3.	Pyrethrum solution	0.5	343

TABLE 3. INSECTICIDAL ACTIVITY OF N-ALKYL-N-(2-CYANOETHYL)-*p*-TOLUENE SULFONAMIDE

Sl. No.	R	Mean 50% knockdown time in seconds
1.	CH ₃	571
2.	C ₂ H ₅	732
3.	C ₃ H ₇	752
4.	Iso-C ₃ H ₇	800

TABLE 4. ETHYL-α-ETHYL-α-(2-CYANOETHYL) MALONANILATE

Sl. No.	R	Mean 50% knockdown time in seconds
1.	2-CH ₃	413
2.	3-CH ₃	400
3.	3-Cl	440
4.	4-Cl	520

TABLE 5. α -METHYL- α -(2-CYANOETHYL) MALONDIANILIDE

Sl. No.	R	Mean 50% knockdown time in seconds
1.	H	406
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	850
3.	4-Cl	836
4.	4-OCH ₃	1153

chlorodianilide. The unsubstituted and the corresponding *p*-methyl substituted compounds were found to be less active.

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TABLE 6. α -ETHYL- α -(2-CYANOETHYL) MALONDIANILIDE

Sl.No.	R	Mean 50% knockdown time in seconds
1.	H	1100
2.	4-CH ₃	960
3.	4-Cl	560

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